

Transient Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Coupling Analyses of a Prismatic Gas-Cooled Reactor Core Using Monte Carlo and Computational Fluid Dynamics Methods

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803468

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a high-fidelity neutronics/thermal-hydraulics transient coupling approach using the Monte Carlo code RMC and the CFD code ANSYS Fluent, and applies transient coupling analyses to the control rod ejection accident in a typical prismatic high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR) core. The high-fidelity coupling scheme is based on Picard iteration, during which RMC time-space dynamics calculation simultaneously updates both the power amplitude and the power shape. Data transferring and mesh mapping are implemented by hierarchical data format (hdf) and multi-superposition mesh mapping strategy to achieve versatility. Various control rod ejection cases, including rod ejected at various locations as well as different equivalent reactivity insertions, are simulated in the prismatic HTGR core. The time-dependent results reflect the thermal-hydraulics feedback, which is amplified as the inserted reactivity increases, indicating that the prismatic HTGR exhibits favorable passive safety characteristics. Comparisons are also made between the results yielded by the high-fidelity approach and the conventional and simplified methods, showing that the results obtained by conventional methods are more fluctuating and overly conservative. The results show that high-fidelity coupling analysis has the merit of reducing the redundant safety margins and enhancing the overall efficiency, and has a certain capability to simulate prompt supercritical transients.

Keywords: Neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupling; Transient coupling; Monte Carlo method; Computational fluid dynamics; High temperature gas-cooled reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demands for reactor efficiency and safety have driven the worldwide focus on high-fidelity numerical simulations for nuclear fission reactors, which seek to reduce the physical approximations of digital reactors to practical applications. The accurate results obtained from high-fidelity methodologies contribute to reducing redundant safety margins and providing calibrations for simplified models. To achieve high-fidelity reactor simulations, it is essential to account for the inherently coupled multiphysics fields inside the core [1]. Among the multiphysics fields, the interaction between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, referred to as neutronics/thermal-hydraulics (N/TH) coupling (Wang et al., 2020), is particularly significant for various reactor types and continues to be the primary focus of reactor multiphysics research.

Many studies have been performed to introduce N/TH coupling approaches using combinations of solvers and analyze N/TH coupling effects in various reactors [2-4]. With the development of advanced new-generation reactor concepts and high-performance computing technologies, more versatile and high-resolution tools, such as Monte Carlo (MC) solvers, and sub-channel and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes, have been increasingly applied following the earlier predominance of deterministic solvers and system analysis codes. Another feature of N/TH coupling studies is that most work has concentrated on steady-state problems, and consequently, the transition towards high-fidelity coupling has also mainly taken place in steady-state analyses [5]. Only a few studies have performed

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high-fidelity transient coupling simulations, with even fewer studying core-level problems. Ferraro et al. conducted a series of studies [6-8], which applied the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2 and the subchannel code SUBCHANFLOW (SCF) to simulate various control rod ejection accidents in various PWR cores, including TMI-1, SPERT III, and the OECD/NRC benchmark. The transient of TMI-1 was simulated for 5 s, while those of SPERT III and the OECD/NRC benchmark were simulated for 1 s.

Furthermore, most existing steady-state and transient coupling research has focused on PWRs, with only a few investigating new-generation reactors, such as the prismatic high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR). In our previous work [9], a versatile coupling approach combining the Monte Carlo code RMC and the CFD code ANSYS Fluent was established, and core-level N/TH coupling analyses were carried out for a typical prismatic HTGR core under steady-state conditions. Based on the steady-state results, this paper performs high-fidelity transient N/TH coupling analyses for the prismatic HTGR using the RMC/Fluent approach. The control rod ejection accident, which induces time-dependent variations in both amplitude and shape of the fields, is studied as a representative transient. This paper aims to make contributions to both transient coupling and high-fidelity numerical simulations of prismatic HTGRs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Computational Tools

2.1.1. Monte Carlo code RMC

This study selected RMC (Reactor Monte Carlo code, version 3.5.1) as the neutronics solver. RMC is a 3-D neutron and photon transport code based on Monte Carlo method developed by the Reactor Engineering Analysis Laboratory (REAL) in Department of Engineering Physics at Tsinghua University [10]. RMC employs Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) together with continuous-energy cross sections to model reactor problems of arbitrary geometrical configurations. RMC has been verified for a wide range of applications, including criticality, burnup, and time-space dynamics analyses, while maintaining high computational efficiency. This study used the time-space dynamics calculation mode for transient analyses, where RMC solves the time-dependent Boltzmann neutron transport equation with the Predictor-Corrector Quasi-Static Monte Carlo (PCQS-MC) method. PCQS-MC method decomposes the angular neutron flux into an amplitude function and a shape function as:

$$\psi(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}, E, t) = T(t)\Psi(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}, E, t), \quad (1)$$

where Ψ represents the shape function, which satisfies the predictor-corrector transient fixed source equation given by:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\bar{\Omega} \cdot \nabla + \Sigma_i(\bar{r}, E, t) + \frac{1}{v\Delta t_{k+1}})\tilde{\Psi}(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}, E, t_{k+1}) - \iint_{\bar{\Omega}', E'} \Sigma_s(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}' \rightarrow \bar{\Omega}, E' \rightarrow E, t)\tilde{\Psi}(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}', E', t_{k+1})d\bar{\Omega}'dE' \\ & = \left[(1 - \beta) \frac{\chi_1(E)}{4\pi} + \sum_i \beta_i \frac{\chi_{2i}(E)}{4\pi} \frac{\lambda_i \Delta t_{k+1}}{1 + \lambda_i \Delta t_{k+1}} \right] \iint_{\bar{\Omega}', E'} v \Sigma_f(\bar{r}, E', t)\tilde{\Psi}(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}', E', t_{k+1})d\bar{\Omega}'dE' + \frac{\Psi(t_k)}{v\Delta t_{k+1}} + \frac{\chi_{2i}(E)}{4\pi} \frac{\lambda_i C_i(t_k)}{1 + \lambda_i \Delta t_{k+1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\Psi(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}, E, t_{k+1}) = \tilde{\Psi}(\bar{r}, \bar{\Omega}, E, t_{k+1}) \frac{\langle \Psi_0 / v, W \rangle}{\langle \tilde{\Psi} / v, W \rangle}, \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{\Psi}$ represents the predicted shape function and W represents the weighting function, which was chosen as the adjoint angular flux of the initial critical state in this study. $T(t)$ in Eq. (1) represents the amplitude function, which satisfies the form of the point kinetics equations given by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = \frac{\rho(t) - \beta(t)}{\Lambda(t)} T(t) + \sum_i \lambda_i c_i(t) \\ \frac{dc_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_i(t)}{\Lambda(t)} T(t) - \lambda_i c_i(t) \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where the point kinetics parameters are dynamically tallied and calculated using Monte Carlo method during iterations. Thus, multiple levels of time step are required to solve Eqs. (1) – (4), as shown in Fig. 1. Δt_{MC} and Δt_P are defined by users, while Δt_k is internally determined in RMC by an embedded Runge-Kutta method with error control. Each RMC calculation in this study used 50 inactive cycles, 300 active cycles, and 500,000 neutrons per cycle.

2.1.2. CFD code ANSYS Fluent

The CFD software ANSYS Fluent (version 2021 R1) was chosen as the thermal-hydraulics solver [11]. ANSYS Fluent provides integrated capabilities for mesh generation, CFD computation, and post-processing based on the finite volume method. Fluent supports a wide range of physical simulations, including fluid flow, solid heat conduction, and combustion. Alternative turbulence models have also been developed, such as Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS), Large Eddy Simulation (LES), and Detached Eddy Simulation (DES). This study employed the RANS equations to describe the conservation of mass, momentum, and energy in turbulent compressible flows, and applied the standard $k-\epsilon$ model to close the RANS equations, where the Reynolds stress term was approximated based on the Boussinesq hypothesis. Considering that Fluent needs to receive the updated power profile transferred from RMC during transient coupling, two levels of time step are also required, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The time discretization scheme in the transient calculation of Fluent.

The CFD simulations throughout this study applied the first-order implicit scheme for the time discretization, the SIMPLE method for the p-v coupling scheme, and the QUICK method for the spatial discretization, unless otherwise specified.

2.2. Picard-based Transient Coupling Scheme

Figure 2 shows the simplified N/TH transient coupling scheme in this study. The routine first initializes the time step information, including the coupling time step, total simulated duration, and the number of sub-time steps for neutronics and thermal-hydraulics fields. The steady-state coupling is performed before the transient coupling, and the steady-state results, including the neutron source distribution, initial power profile, and initial thermal-hydraulics data are used as the initial condition of the entire transient coupling. $k_{eff} = 1$ is guaranteed in the steady-state results by adjusting the material composition, or the geometry. The routine then invoked a typical Picard-based iteration procedure in each time step, which are presented in Fig. 2. The coupling time step, Δt , was set to be equal to Δt_{MC} and Δt_{CFD} .

Figure 2. Picard-based transient N/TH coupling scheme using RMC/ANSYS Fluent.

The data transfer and mesh mapping are keys to implementing the coupling scheme, since the data structures, file formats, and solution elements differ significantly between Monte Carlo and CFD solvers. In this study, the hdf5 file was adopted as a unified I/O format shared by both RMC and Fluent, which avoided intermediate the text file to improve the data transfer efficiency and precision. The ‘multi-superposition’ strategy was applied to implement mesh mapping, which avoided the direct interact between the MC cells and CFD meshes by separating the solver mesh from the statistical mesh to achieve geometry-independence. The technical details and the optimization effects have been presented in our earlier publication [9]. Under-relaxation with a factor of 0.5 was also applied to the data being transferred to improve convergence.

3. THE PRISMATIC HTGR MODEL

The core model analyzed in this study adopts a typical prismatic HTGR design. Figure 3 presents the detailed layout of the core and the fuel assembly. The model represents a micro modular HTGR operating at 3 MPa with the full power of 4 MW_{th}. The helium coolant enters the horizontal core through an annular channel located between the core basket and the reactor vessel wall, with an inlet temperature of 445°C and a mass flow of 2.525 kg/s, then flows inward across the active core and exits on the opposite side, as shown by the blue-to-red gradient arrow. The core is assembled from one central and six peripheral control assemblies, carbon brick shields, graphite reflectors, and fuel assemblies. Each control assembly is composed of natural enriched B₄C, and each fuel assembly has three identical axial layers containing 6 inner assemblies and 24 outer assemblies loaded with TRISO-dispersed fuel elements. The inner assemblies load 17wt% enriched fuel while the outer assemblies load 19.75wt% enriched fuel. Each fuel assembly is composed of a hexagonal graphite block, which contains fuel channels arranged in a triangular lattice and coolant channels located at the vertices of the hexagonal lattice. Each fuel channel contains twenty columnar fuel elements stacked along the axial direction, with graphite sealing both ends. Each fuel element consists of a SiC matrix containing TRISO particles at a volume fraction of 40%.

Figure 3. Detailed layout of the HTGR core used in this study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Simulation Conditions

Multiple steady-state coupling calculations were performed first to determine the critical control rod position. RMC criticality calculation and Fluent steady-state calculation were repeatedly executed in each steady-state coupling calculation following a similar Picard-based scheme to that presented in our previous work [9], while the peripheral control rod heights were adjusted to drive the reactor core towards criticality. The criticality was achieved at $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00001 \pm 0.00005$ with the peripheral control rod height of 97.8 cm.

The transient was initiated by a control rod ejection accident, during which the peripheral control rods were extracted at a constant velocity for 0 - 1 s, and remained stationary for 1 - 10 s, giving a total simulation time of 10 s. Two cases were analyzed with the equivalent static reactivity insertions of 500 pcm and 750 pcm. The specific ejecting velocities were set to be 4.5 cm/s and 7.0 cm/s such that the resulting static reactivity insertions were equal to the expected values. The transient coupling simulations used a coupling time step $\Delta t = 0.2$ s, resulting in a total of 50 steps. Each step was further divided into 20 sub-steps in both RMC and Fluent, giving $\Delta t_P = \Delta t_{\text{subCFD}} = 0.01$ s. All simulations were executed in parallel on a Linux server with 64 processors and 256 GB of memory.

4.2. Transient Coupling Results and Analyses

All coupling calculations in each time step converged within 4 Picard iterations. Figure 4 presents the transient coupling results of the time-dependent lumped parameters including the core thermal power, maximum and average fuel temperature, and the reactivity and its decompositions for various control rod ejection cases. For the case with a 500 pcm equivalent reactivity insertion, the core thermal power increases with time during the control rod ejection as expected. After the control rods stop moving, the thermal power exhibits a slight increase for a certain period before gradually decreasing. Meanwhile, for the case with a 750 pcm equivalent reactivity insertion, the thermal power rapidly increases with time during the ejection and then decreases after the control rod stops. Both the maximum and the average fuel temperatures continuously increase with time, and the increasing rate is proportional to the thermal power. The fuel temperature rise in turn induces negative reactivity feedback, which compensates the positive reactivity inserted by the control rod ejection. As a result, in the case with an equivalent static reactivity insertion of 750 pcm, the maximum reactivity during the transient only slightly exceeded 1 \$ for a very short time, making this case essentially a delayed supercritical transient. Compared with the 500 pcm case, the power amplitude in the 750 pcm case increases more rapidly during the ejection as expected, leading to a higher temperature rise, which results in more negative reactivity feedback. The stronger feedback in turn drives the power to decrease more rapidly. The

differences in monotonicity arise from the complex nature of reactor dynamics, where the transient response is governed by the time-dependent reactivity and strongly influenced by specific numerical values, and thus cannot be reliably predicted by simple empirical or qualitative intuition. Figure 4 does not present the variations of the coolant density and other material temperatures, since the density of helium and its variation are relatively small, and the fuel temperature is the dominant factor in the thermal-hydraulic feedback of prismatic HTGRs as shown in our previous study [9]. This characteristic also represents one of the main differences compared with conventional PWR coupling.

Figure 4. Transient coupling results of the lumped variables including (a) core thermal power, (b) maximum and average fuel temperature, and (c) reactivity and its decompositions.

The results in this section also indicate that the prismatic HTGR exhibits favorable passive safety characteristics, which primarily rely on the negative reactivity feedback of the fuel temperature.

4.3. Comparative Analysis of High-Fidelity and Conventional Methods

This section compares the results obtained with the high-fidelity coupling method with those from the conventional approaches for a prismatic HTGR to further demonstrate the necessity of the high-fidelity method. Although various transient coupling methods superficially differ in terms of solvers and reactor types, their fundamental distinction arises from the power treatment. The power updating methods can be summarized into three categories, including two conventional approaches and a high-fidelity method as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Three typical methods to update the power profile during transient coupling, (a) and (b) represent two conventional methods, and (c) represents the high-fidelity method.

All methods share the common feature of first decomposing the power profile into an amplitude function and a shape function. Method (a) assumes that the shape function remains fixed at the steady-state distribution, and updates the amplitude using point kinetics equations, with the point kinetics parameters taken as constants and the reactivity calculated from thermal-hydraulics results and tabulated feedback coefficients. Method (b) represents an improvement of method (a), in which the criticality calculation is performed by the neutronics solver to update both the reactivity and the shape function. Method (c) has the highest fidelity of the three approaches, where both the amplitude and the shape function are updated by time-space dynamics calculation.

The above methods were then applied to simulate the rod ejection cases and compare the transient coupling results, with the simulation conditions identical to those presented in Sec. 4.1. All coupling calculations in each time step converged within 4 Picard iterations. Figure 6 shows the variations of the core thermal power with time for various cases. Figure 6 first shows that the results obtained by conventional methods (a) (in blue) and (b) (in red) exhibit more significant fluctuations compared with the high-fidelity method (c) (in black), and the fluctuations are most pronounced in the most simplified method (a). The fluctuations arise because the point kinetics model used in conventional approaches, which does not dynamically update the point kinetics parameters, overestimates the total power variation within a coupling time step, which in turn leads to an overestimation of the thermal-hydraulics feedback and eventually produces the observed fluctuations. The results also show that the fluctuations are amplified as the reactivity insertion increases.

Moreover, the results show that conventional methods (a) and (b) predict a faster increase in total power during the control rod ejection, followed by a more rapid and fluctuating decrease after the rods stop compared with the high-fidelity method. The power peak obtained by method (a) is the largest, whereas that of the high-fidelity method is the smallest, and the peak difference is amplified as the positive reactivity insertion increases. The comparison indicates that, compared with the high-fidelity approach, the conventional methods tend to yield overly conservative results, and the redundancy increases with the level of simplification.

Figure 6. Transient coupling results of the time-dependent core power obtained by various methods, with the equivalent static reactivity insertions = (a) 500 pcm and (b) 750 pcm.

The observation precisely reflects the fundamental objective of high-fidelity coupling, which is to reduce the redundant safety margins and thus to enhance the overall efficiency, while maintaining a higher level of safety than decoupled approaches. Thus, it can be inferred that the high-fidelity transient coupling approach has a certain capability to simulate prompt supercritical transients, which are difficult to address effectively with conventional coupling methods.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a high-fidelity neutronics/thermal-hydraulics transient coupling approach using the Monte Carlo code RMC and the CFD code ANSYS Fluent and applies transient coupling analyses

to the control rod ejection accident in a typical prismatic HTGR core. In the coupling scheme, RMC performs time-space dynamics calculation using the Predictor-Corrector Quasi-Static Monte Carlo (PCQS-MC) method, Fluent performs transient calculation, and Picard iteration is applied in each time step.

This study simulates several control rod ejection cases in a prismatic HTGR core, in which the rods are first ejected at a constant speed and then held stationary. These cases involve different equivalent reactivity insertions. The high-fidelity transient simulations yield time-evolving results that reflect the thermal-hydraulics feedback. The results also indicate that the prismatic HTGR exhibits favorable passive safety characteristics, which primarily rely on the negative reactivity feedback of the fuel temperature. The comparison of the results yielded by the high-fidelity approach with those obtained by conventional and simplified methods shows that the high-fidelity coupling analysis has the merit of reducing the redundant safety margins and thus enhancing the overall efficiency. This study provides insights into both transient coupling and high-fidelity numerical simulations, with particular emphasis on prismatic HTGRs. More transient scenarios, such as the loss of flow accident, loss of coolant accident, and start-up analysis, should be considered in the future.

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